

EFFECT OF STUDENT–TEACHER CONFERENCE TUTORING ON STUDENTS’ ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY, IN MKPAT ENIN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of student–teacher conference tutoring on students’ academic performance in biology, focusing on the concept of Cell. The influence of gender on students’ performance under conference tutoring and conventional teaching methods was also examined. A quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design was adopted. The sample comprised of one hundred (100) Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students drawn from two co-educational public secondary schools in Mkpata Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The experimental group was taught using the student–teacher conference tutoring strategy, while the control group were taught using conventional teaching method. Data were collected using a validated Biology Performance Test (BPT) and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and independent t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed a significant improvement in students’ academic performance when taught using student–teacher conference tutoring compared to the conventional method. However, no significant gender differences were observed in students’ performance under both instructional strategies. The study concludes that student–teacher conference tutoring is an effective and gender-neutral instructional strategy for improving students’ achievement in Biology.

Keywords: *Effect, Student–teacher, conference, tutoring, students’ academic performance*

Introduction

The primary purpose of teaching at any level of education is to bring a fundamental change in the learner (Tebabal & Kahssay, 2015). Many teaching practitioners widely applied teacher-centered methods to impart knowledge to learners, comparative to student-centered methods. Questions about the effectiveness of teaching methods on student learning have consistently raised considerable interest in the thematic field of educational research (Hightower, 2018). Moreover, research on teaching and learning constantly endeavor to examine the extent to which different teaching methods enhance growth in student learning. According to Ayeni (2014), teaching is a process that involves bringing about desirable changes in learners so as to achieve specific outcomes. In order for the method used for teaching to be

effective, Adunola (2019) maintains that teachers need to be conversant with numerous teaching strategies that take recognition of the magnitude of complexity of the concepts to be covered.

Teachers’ delivery of lessons is very vital to educational quality. Instructional methods are ways or modes of how information is presented to students. Such methods falls into two categories; teachers centered approach and students centered approach. The teacher centered approach feature low levels of students’ choice, passive students, and power residing primarily with the teacher. Learners or students centered approach does not necessarily control the learning process to students (although some power sharing is often involved) but takes into account the knowledge, skills,

attitude and beliefs that learners bring to the educational setting (Akpokiniovo, 2022). There is no one best approach to instructional delivery. Some objectives are better suited to teacher-centered approaches while others clearly need student centered approach (Roff, 2021).

Biology is regarded as a life science because it encompasses the study of living things. It teaches different forms of organic life and their relations with the environment and other sciences. Biology is relevant to our lives, through the knowledge of Biology, we know how the body functions and, the organs that are in the body, learn about life in our environment. It also helps us to know our genetic makeup and prevent some genetic disorders and diseases. Biology can also tell us about plants of major importance and their benefits to our body systems. Biology is one of the foundational subjects for many professional courses such as Medicine, Biochemistry, Pharmacy, Microbiology and Agriculture among others.

In spite of the significance of this subject to human survival, the recital of upper secondary students of Biology is not encouraging. The poor academic performance is indicated in the report of WAEC and the National Teacher Institute (2011). Dinah (2013) stated that the inadequate availability of textbooks and the use of conventional methods of teaching have an immense impact on the performance of students in Biology examinations. Therefore, there is a need to look into a more student-centered approach to teaching. Teaching strategy are tools use in teaching, they are used based on the objectives the teachers hope to achieved, some of them are like workshops example conference tutoring, problem-based learning, questioning and discussion, problem-solving, demonstration and Laboratory work methods are being used today to pass instruction to students, thus improving the quality of education (Ajaja, 2013).

However, teachers cannot master the various teaching method without adequate training through workshop and conference/seminar attendance. Conference in education entails the coming together of diverse personnel who are experts in education with a view to sharing of ideas. Conferencing can be teacher-teacher based or student-teacher based. Robinson (2016) hold that conferencing is a useful tool for gaining feedback from students and helping them reach high levels of achievement in the classroom. It allows teachers the opportunity to assess students and individualize instruction.

Conference tutoring is a one-on-one discussion between students and teachers to take stock of student's needs, the conference usually involves a discussion of both strengths as well as areas for improvement (Leung, 2018). The conference should conclude with a list of goals for the teacher and student to mutually strive toward. According to Osakinle, Onijigin, and Falaba, (2017), student-teacher conferences tutoring plays a vital role in discussing the needs, requirements and progress of the student. In a time when connecting with students is no easy task, these conferences can be a lifesaver. Good communication is essential in every classroom. It is crucial for the development of an effective student-teacher relationship (Assaggaf, Stapa, & Mustafa, 2019). Conference tutoring can help inspire and boost student interest in science-oriented subject such as Biology, Mathematics, Physic, Chemistry etc.

Many variables have been responsible for students learning out comes in biology, but teaching strategy is the most upsetting as it has great effect on the students' academic performance (Almaz, 2019), (Arriasseq, I. & Guridi, (2020). Obiekwe and Oludipe (2013) have independently shown that the teaching of science in Nigerian secondary schools falls short of the standard expected of it. Most of the teaching strategy used has been described as inappropriate and uninspiring (Igboegwu,

2014). One major problem of the teachers is the inability to deploy appropriate and innovative teaching strategy such as conference tutoring. Effective learning and sound academic performance contribute to national development. It is something of great importance to parents, teachers and students themselves; even the larger society is aware of the long-term effects of high and low academic performance since the product of schools are expected to shape the destiny of the society. The main prerequisite for learners to get assistance from this innovative teaching strategy (conference tutoring) depends on the level of teacher understanding of this vital teaching strategy (conference tutoring) and realizing essential teaching skills to be deploy by teachers.

Accordingly, this implies that in carrying out a change in methods of teaching a subject such as Biology is to discover through experimentation and empirical evidence that such method can yield effective instructional outcomes. To arrest students' attention, interest, curiosity and promote their performance, the use of activity stimulating and student-centered approach like conference tutoring teaching strategy is essential instead of depending on the conventional method. Gender remains an important factor to be considered in the determination of students' academic achievement. Gender is a psychological term describing behavior and attributes expected of individuals on the basis of being male or female (Umanah, 2017).

Gender is the perception we have about male and female, the relation between them and their social organization. Omiko (2017) defined gender as the relationship between men and women both perceptual and material. Gender is not determined biologically, as a result of sexual characteristics of either women or men, but is constructed socially. It is a central organizing principle of societies, and often governs the processes of production and reproduction,

consumption and distribution. Oludipe (2012) highlighted the four genders of noun in English as: masculine, feminine, common, and neuter. Masculine nouns refer to words for a male figure or male member of a species (i.e. man, boy, actor, horse, etc.), Feminine nouns refer to female figures or female members of a species (i.e. woman, girl, actress, mare, etc.), Common nouns refer to members of a species and don't specify the gender (i.e. parent, friend, client, student, etc.) and neuter nouns refer to things that have no gender (i.e. rock, table, pencil, etc.).

Gender issues have been linked with performance of students in academic task in several studies but without any definite conclusion. The issue of parity and disparity in the performance of male and female students in science has formed an important focus of research for some years now (Alio and Harbor-Peters 2018). Calsmith (2017) explain that the influence of gender difference in academic performance is a complex task, thus many studies appear to be contradicting. Gender has a concept calls for research review from time to time. Gender differences in students' performance have been of great concern to biology educators, yet research findings have been inconsistent. Some researchers are of the opinion that male students perform academically better than female students, others found the opposite; on the other hand, other researchers found no differences at all between male and female students' academic performance in biology. There is therefore need to use teaching strategy that encourage gender equality, positive interdependence and group work so as to motivate the students for higher academic performance.

To enhance the academic performance of students, there is a great need to turn from conventional teaching strategy to modern teaching strategy. Conference tutoring is a modern teaching strategy for teachers to go through in other to enhance students' academic

performance. Conference tutoring is student-centered, interactive and integrative. It provides a non-threatening atmosphere for students as it creates confidence in them. It helps students to take charge of the process and also share their challenges and difficulties during the learning process, evaluates their cognitive ability writing, and exposes them to life experience in classroom. It is therefore in the light of the foregoing that this study therefore examines conference tutoring teaching strategy on students' academic performance in chemistry in Mkpato Enin Local Government of Akwa Ibom State.

iii.

Statement of the Problem

During teaching and learning process, the cardinal objective is to see that the learner/student should be able to perform tasks and if possible, transfer the experience in solving problems in a new situation. This objective has hardly been achieved over the 1 years. The rate of failure in internal and external examination in chemistry in recent times is a matter of concern. The question is that “does teaching strategy affects student’s academic 2 performance in biology in secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?”

It is strongly believed that the teaching strategy 3 adopted by biology teacher in teaching biology is to a large extent responsible for the consistent poor performance in biology. This is because the teaching strategy used by biology teachers were teacher centered and do not allow students’ participation, therefore imposing poor concept formation and reducing interest of the students. in biology. It is on this basis that the study seeks to investigate the effect of student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy on students’ academic performance in biology in Mkpato Enin Local Government of Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the effect of student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy on students’ academic performance in biology in Mkpato Enin Local Government of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study intends to achieve the following objectives;

To assess the mean performance scores of biology students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy and conventional method.

To assess the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy.

To assess the mean performance scores between male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean performance score of biology students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy and conventional method?

2. What difference exist in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy?

3. What differences exist in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

There is no significance difference in the mean performance score of chemistry students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy and conventional method.

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring teaching strategy.

iii. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method.

Research Method

The research design for the study was quasi-experimental design. This design was most suitable as it attempts to establish a cause-and-effect relationship by using criteria other than randomization. The population of the study comprised of all senior secondary two students (SS1) in all the sixteen (16) public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area and it is about one thousand four hundred and two (1,402) students (Local Education Committee, L.E.C 2023).

The sample size for this study was one hundred (100) students, (50-Male and 50-Female) in their intact class from two (2) co-educational public schools which was randomly selected from the sixteen (16) public co-educational secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The instrument to be employed in this study for data collection was a researcher made Performance test tagged “Biology Performance Test (BPT)”. The Biology Performance Test (BPT) contained twenty five (25) items with options lettered A-D of which only one option is the correct answer and the other two served as distracters.

A lesson plan was developed by the researcher. The reliability of the Instruments was determined using a sample of twenty (20) Senior Secondary one (SS1) Students. The twenty (20) students were selected from a school that is not part of the research area. The scores were analyzed using reliability index Kuder Richardson Reliability formula $20(K-R20)$ to ascertain the internal consistency in which a value of 0.77 was obtained and considered high. This high value showed that the instrument is reliable. The students were randomly assigned to two groups. Group one were taught the concept of Cell using conference tutoring and Group two were taught the same concept using Conventional method. After teaching the concept of Cell, the Biology Performance Test (BPT) were administered to the students and after the test, the answer scripts were retrieved, marked and recorded for data analysis. The data generated from the retrieved instruments was analyzed using appropriate statistical tool. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using independent t-test.

Results

Research Question One: What is the difference in the mean performance score of chemistry student taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher conference tutoring and conventional method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of biology students taught the concept of Cell using Student-teacher Conference Tutoring and Conventional Method?

Instructional Strategy	N	SD	SD	SD	Mean Gain Scores	
STC Tutoring	50	29.61	16.51	45.71	27.36	16.81
Conventional Method	50	28.90	16.29	39.60	23.34	9.99

Table 1 showed the academic performance mean score of students taught the concept of Cell using conference tutoring had post-test,

pre-test, mean gain difference of 16.81 while those taught the concept of Cell using conventional method had 9.99 respectively.

This observation implies that biology student taught using conference tutoring had the best performance than students taught using conventional method. This observation answered Research Question one.

Research Question Two. What difference exists in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of cell using conference tutoring.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using student-teacher Conference Tutoring

Gender	N	X	SD	X	SD	Mean Gain Scores
Male	24	35.21	15.14	41.67	25.77	6.46
Female	26	23.08	15.81	37.69	21.17	14.01

In Table 2, the results showed academic performance mean scores of male and female students taught the concept of cell using conference tutoring had mean gain difference of 6.46 and 14.01 respectively. This observation showed that female students had the best performance in the concept of Cell.

This observation therefore answered research question two

Research Question Three: What difference exists in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Conventional method?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method

Gender	n	X	SD	X	SD	Mean Gain Scores
Male	26	35.96	15.68	47.69	30.41	11.73
Female	24	21.64	13.86	42.50	24.04	20.86

In Table 3, the results showed the academic performance mean scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method had post-test pretest difference of 11.73 and 20.86 respectively. This indicates that female biology students had the best mean gain scores than their male counterpart. This observation therefore answered research question three.

Testing the Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of chemistry student taught the concept of Cell using Student-teacher Conference Tutoring and Conventional method.

Table 4: Independence – t-test analysis of post-test score of chemistry student taught the concept of Cell using Conference Tutoring and Conventional Method.

Instructional strategies	N	SD	df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision @ p < .05
STC tutoring	50	45.71	98	2.19	1.98	S
Conventional Method	50	39.60	23.34			

Where NS = not significant

In Table 4, the t - calculated value for the main effect of instructional strategies on the students' academic performance is 2.19 and its t - critical value at df 2, 98 is 1.98. This level of significance is greater than 0.05 alpha. This implies that the effect of instructional strategies on students' performance was statistically significant. That is, there significant effect of instructional strategies on

students' academic performance. Hence, null Hypothesis one, which says "There is no significant difference in the concept of Cell using Conference Tutoring and the Conventional method was rejected.

Hypothesis Two. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Conference Tutoring

Table 5: Independent t - test analysis of post test scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Student-teacher Conference Tutoring

Gender	n	X	SD	df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision @ < .05
Male	24	41.67	15.14	48	-1.19	2.01	NS
Female	26	37.69	15.81				

Where NS = not significant

In Table 5, the calculated t - value for the main effect of Gender is - 1.19 at df2, 48 while its corresponding t - critical value is 2.01. This observation shows that gender had no statistically significant on the academic performance of chemistry students in the concept of Cel. Hence, Hypothesis Two: which stated "There is no significant difference

between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Conference Tutoring was retained.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method.

Table 6: Independent - t - test analysis of post test scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using conventional method.

Gender	N	X	SD	df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision
Male	26	47.69	30.41	48	-1.19	2.01	NS
Female	24	42.50	24.04				

Where NS = not significant

In Table 6, the calculated value for the main effect of gender at df 2, 48 is -1.19 while its corresponding t - critical value is 2.01. This observation shows that gender is not a determinant on students' academic performance. Hypothesis 3 which stated " There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Charles' law using conventional method was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The following deduction were made after the analysis and interpretation of data:

There is statistically significant difference in the mean performance scores of chemistry students taught the concept of Cell using Students-teacher Conference Tutoring and Conventional method. This finding supports

the Social Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasizes learning through guided interaction and scaffolding provided by a more knowledgeable individual (Vygotsky, 1978). It also agrees with Ajaja (2013), who reported that student-centered instructional strategies significantly improve students' academic achievement compared to traditional lecture methods. Similarly, Echoga (2019) found that students taught using conference-based instructional methods performed significantly better than those taught using conventional approaches.

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Students-teacher Conference Tutoring. This finding aligned with the work of Iji, Ochu, Adikwu & Atamonokhai, (2017), who reported no significant gender difference in students' academic achievement when exposed to interactive and collaborative instructional strategies. Godpower-Echie & Ihenko (2017) similarly observed that gender had no significant influence on students' academic achievement when effective teaching strategies were employed. The result suggests that the effectiveness of instructional strategies outweighs gender as a determinant of academic performance in Biology.

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught the concept of Cell using Conventional method. This finding is consistent with Oludipe (2012), who found no significant gender difference in students' academic achievement in science subjects when exposed to similar teaching conditions. It also supports the findings of Calsmith (2017), who noted that gender differences in academic performance are inconsistent and often dependent on contextual and instructional factors rather than biological differences. The result further suggests that the conventional

teaching method affects male and female students similarly, though less effectively than student-teacher conference tutoring.

Conclusion

Instructional strategies differ significantly in their effects on academic performance of students in Biology. Effective teaching and learning of Biology is based on the ability of the teachers to select and use the most appropriate instructional strategies. The performances of the students are also higher when they are exposed to activities during class instructions.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Students should be properly exposed to the right teaching strategies such as conference tutoring in order to enhance their participation in science activities and facilitate easy understanding of lessons and skills acquisition.
- ii. Teachers should utilize instructional media in order to arouse and sustain students' interest.
- iii. Biology teachers should be sensitized to use effective instructional strategy to improve students' understanding and academic performance.

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